

Differences in photosynthetic rates of six rice varieties under low (15 °C). A = Wuyugeng, B = Yayou 2, C = Tsukushibare, D = Shanhou 63, E = Nanjing 14, F = Xiangxian.

using a Clark O₂ electrode and compared with the photosynthetic rate at optimum temperatures of 30-35 °C. The

ratio of photosynthesis under high and low temperature to that of optimum temperature was represented as a high- or low-temperature tolerance index. Six varieties were selected for their tolerance for temperature stress (see figure). The results showed that japonica rice Wuyugeng and indica-japonica hybrid Yayou 2 were tolerant of both high and low temperatures. Their photosynthetic rates were stable. Under field conditions, japonica rice Wuyugeng is tolerant of light and temperature stresses and its yield has been relatively stable at more than 9 t ha⁻¹.

Wuyugeng is now one of the main rice varieties in Jiangsu Province, China. On the contrary, indica rice Xiangxian, which is sensitive to light and temperature stresses, has not been grown in Jiangsu.

In general, the types adapted to wide ranges of light and temperature were mostly japonica and indica-japonica rice varieties. In the region near the middle or lower reaches of the Yangtze River, selecting japonica rice and indica-japonica hybrid rice varieties adapted to wide ranges of light and temperature stresses may be an approach for rice breeders to use for obtaining high and stable yield. ■

Stress tolerance — adverse soils

Variation in salt tolerance among rice mutants and varieties based on yield attributes

L. M. Gonzalez, R. Lopez, and R. Ramirez, Nuclear Laboratory, Agricultural Research Institute Jorge Dimitrov, Gaveta Postal 2360, Bayamo 85100, Granma, Cuba

Around 100,000 of the 160,000 ha determined to be suitable for rice production in Cuba are affected by salt. We have therefore focused our rice breeding program on obtaining salt-tolerant genotypes.

We evaluated 9 mutants obtained from the J-112 variety through gamma radiation and 19 varieties for salt-tolerance field studies. The genotypes were studied in specially designed 3- × 3- × 1-m test plots in saline soil (plastic dark Gley Typic, with pH 7.44, 2000 ppm of total soluble solids, 0.90% organic matter, 0.003% N, 5.51 mg P100 g⁻¹ soil, and 11.68% mg K 100 g⁻¹ soil), and in nonstressed productive soil over two seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. The crops were managed following local practices. Data on agronomic attributes (panicle length, panicle weight, filled grains

Clustering pattern among 28 rice genotypes and cluster means based on the saline stress tolerance indexes for different characters.

Cluster	Strains in each cluster	Saline stress tolerance index (%) based on				
		Panicle length	Panicle weight	Filled grains panicle ⁻¹	1000-grain weight	Grain yield
A	Theoretical check	100	100	100	100	100
B	RM12, RM62, RM41, RM66, RM114, RM157, RM72, RM120, RM153	92	90	90	88	50
C	IACUBA-26, Caribe I, IR5931, IR42, J112, 4024, 2006, CP3-C2, J104	88	80	85	83	45
D	Amistad-82, 6140	70	52	80	77	39
E	2005, 4014, IR8, 4032, 4034, MI-48, Perla	62	45	72	70	34

panicle⁻¹, 1000-grain weight, and grain yield) were collected from 10 randomly selected plants in each replication.

For all dates collected in the experiment, the saline stress tolerance index was calculated. To study the genotypic variation in the above characters, the data were processed further by using cluster analysis through Euclidian distance, including a theoretical check (100%) for all saline stress tolerance indexes.

In general, salinity markedly reduced agronomic attributes in all genotypes. Based on the Euclidian distance values, the population of 28 genotypes was grouped in 4 clusters (B, C, D, E) (see figure), indicating a great

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

Euclidean distance

Dendrogram of clustering for radiomutants and varieties based on saline stress tolerance index for yield and yield attributes.

variability for salt tolerance. Cluster B, consisting of 9 mutants from the J-112 variety, had the highest mean for all attributes (see table), as well as the minimum value of intercluster distance with a theoretical check (cluster A), a result indicating that the mutants grouped in it were the most tolerant of those tested.

Clusters C and D consisted of 10 and 2 genotypes, respectively. These genotypes were intermediate in salt tolerance.

Seven genotypes comprised cluster E. These genotypes present a lower value of means for all attributes and a maximum intercluster distance value with cluster A (theoretical check), indicating they are the most susceptible. In this cluster were two varieties (MI 48 and IR8) that many breeders use as a susceptible checks. This finding confirmed our method used in varietal tolerance evaluation.

Our results indicated that the mutants grouped in cluster A were higher than the parent and other varieties for salt tolerance, indicating the possibility of generating heritable variation for this attribute in rice through gamma radiation. The varieties hold promise in salt-affected areas and may also serve as donor parents in breeding for salt tolerance. ■

Water relations in rice seedlings in saline medium

L. M. González and R. Ramírez, Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry Department, Agricultural Research Institute Jorge Dimitrov, Gaveta Postal 2360, Bayamo 85100, Granma, Cuba

We evaluated the seedling water content (SWC), leaf relative water content (LRWC), transpiration intensity (TI), and the cell sap concentration (CSC) in four rice varieties, differentiated by the degree of their salt tolerance. Pokkali and IR24 were tested

for salt tolerance and MI 48 and Perla for susceptible behavior.

Seedlings of four varieties were sown in nutrient solution under controlled laboratory conditions using Hoagland nutrient solution (control) and Hoagland nutrient solution

Effect of salinity on some water relation variables in rice seedlings. Granma, Cuba. ^a

Variety	Seedling water content (%)		Leaf relative water content (%)		Transpiration (mg H ₂ O mg DW ⁻¹ h ⁻²)		Cell sap concentration (% TSS) ^b	
	Control	Stress	Control	Stress	Control	Stress	Control	Stress
Pokkali	89 ± 0.84	82 ± 1.16**	88 ± 0.12	80 ± 0.90**	5.1 ± 0.10	3.6 ± 0.52**	5.9 ± 0.06	9.1 ± 0.17***
IR42	87 ± 0.76	80 ± 0.68**	87 ± 0.51	78 ± 1.25**	4.8 ± 0.65	3.2 ± 0.45**	5.5 ± 0.22	8.9 ± 0.03***
MI 48	89 ± 0.47	71 ± 0.46***	86 ± 0.23	69 ± 0.12**	6.0 ± 0.10	2.7 ± 0.22***	5.2 ± 0.10	8.2 ± 0.20***
Perla	92 ± 0.47	69 ± 0.48***	85 ± 0.82	69 ± 0.70**	5.4 ± 0.38	1.9 ± 0.06***	5.1 ± 0.20	8.3 ± 0.47***

^a** and *** = significant differences for P < 0.01 and P < 0.001 by the Student-t test. ^bTSS = total soluble salts.